

THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF PARTICULATE REINFORCED ALUMINUM ALLOY AT ELEVATED TEMPERATURE

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SUMMARY: The deformation characteristics at elevated temperature of aluminium alloy 6061 reinforced with particulate SiC have been investigated. The materials investigated contained 10% by volume and 10 μ m by size of SiC particulates. In order to set up a comparative materials data base, the microstructural characteristics of the unreinforced matrix material with identical fabricating and processing history were examined. The results show that at room temperature, the compressive strength of the SiC 10/10/6061Al composite is higher than 6061Al alloy, and there is not so much difference between 200~25°C. But at elevated temperature, the compressive strength of the SiC 10/10/6061Al composite is less than 6061Al alloy.

KEYWORDS: metal matrix composites, particulate reinforced, thermal mechanical property

INTRODUCTION

Metal matrix composites (MMCs) have been developed in the last few years, in order to reduce the weight of components in structural applications and to improve their thermal and mechanical properties. Particulate reinforced MMCs have the advantage of being machinable and workable using conventional processing methods. The particulate-reinforced metal matrix composites have been widely applied to the aerospace industry, because of their desirable properties, including low density, high specific stiffness, and increased wear resistance.

The influence of matrix microstructure and the morphology of the particulate reinforced composite on the compressive strength at elevated temperature is still not clear. In order to reveal the influence of the strengthening mechanism, the compressive tests have been studied on the silicon carbide particulate reinforced aluminum at various temperature. It attempts to characterize their behaviour on experimental observations of the matrix microstructure and reinforcement morphology on uniaxial stress-strain response of the 10/10/6061Al composite. The mechanisms of strengthening and failure in metal matrix composites have been issues of academic research for some time. Many different mechanisms have been proposed. These include: (1) load transfer between the matrix and reinforcement [1,2,3], (2) enhanced

dislocation density in the matrix [4,5], (3) matrix and interfacial precipitation [6,7]. In addition to the wide range of viewpoints on the strengthening of MMCs, there were a variety of failure mechanisms have been reported. These include: (1) cavitation at the interface and within the matrix [8,9,10], (2) ductile failure in the matrix of the composite [11, 12], particle cracking [13], and (4) interfacial decohesion [14]. A recent study has shown aging induced precipitation and microstructure evolution in the matrix of SiC reinforced Al-6061 to be quite different from the unreinforced control alloy which was subjected to identical heat treatment [15]. Such differences in the precipitation kinetics will affect the strength of the composite more than details of strengthening theories such as the rule of mixtures, which assumes the matrix of the composite to be unaffected by the presence of reinforcement.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

The mechanical properties of particulate reinforced MMCs are controlled by a complex interaction between the matrices and reinforcements. The addition of a reinforcing phase of different elastic properties induces strain concentrations. In order to maintain the displacement compatibility across the interface when a far-field strain is applied, dislocations are generated at the composite interface. Also, the difference in thermal expansion coefficients between the two phases necessitates the generation of dislocations to accommodate thermal strain on changing temperature. The interaction of matrix dislocations, with precipitates and with the reinforcing phase determines the mechanical behaviour of the composite. The aim of this study was to study the effect of systematic variations in reinforcement volume fraction, particle size and heat treatment on the mechanical behaviour of SiC reinforced Al-6061. The model materials consisted of a matrix metal (6061Al) and 10% vol. 10 μ m of silicon carbide particulate reinforced composite, as shown in Fig.1. Uniaxial compression test was performed on cylindrical specimens (ϕ :9mm, L:10mm) at various temperature (RT, 100, 150, 200, 250, and 400°C). Before testing, the specimens were isothermal exposure in the testing box 30min at every stage. The results of the 10/10/6061Al composite and pure 6061Al alloy at various temperature are shown in Fig. 2, and Fig. 3. The strength of the 10/10/6061Al composite between RT and 150°C is higher than 6061Al alloy, and no significant difference between 200°C and 250°C, but lower than expected from 250~400°C. The additional reinforcing particles in the composite is the dominant effect on compressive strength at RT~250°C. But at higher temperature the strength afforded by the reinforced particle varied with temperature and matrix temper. The fractographic section of the thermal compressive specimen 10/10/6061Al on SEM is shown in Fig. 4. The composite compressive fracture section on higher temperature exhibit that fewer SiC particles are cracking, and the voids nucleated near by the SiC particles. The voids (2 μ m) most likely nucleate by cracking of the particles.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The 10/10/6061Al composite and 6061Al alloy exhibit different thermal mechanical properties. The additional reinforcing particles to the 6061Al matrix metal can increase the compressive stress at room temperature, but decrease at elevated temperature. The main reasons are discussed as follow:

At room temperature:

1. The additional silicon carbide hard particles are presented in softer matrix, they hinder dislocations motion, and enhance the composite strength.
2. The difference in coefficient of thermal expansion

(CTE) between the two phases have been related to a high dislocation density in the matrix. The CTE of aluminum is seven times larger than that of SiC, the thermal mismatch strains occurring at the interface hence high density dislocations and the particles are obstacle to the dislocation movement. This enhances the composite strength as well[16].

At elevated temperature:

1. The thermal mechanical properties of the particulates reinforced composite are controlled by interaction between the matrices and reinforced particles, if the particulate are well bonded to the matrix. However, the SiC particles may be broken, or debonded with the matrix, and left the voids. This induce the displacement discontinuity, and reduce the resistant strength. So that, the matrix deformation play a key role in the thermal compression behavior. At higher temperature, the particles on the matrix, induce an incoherent effect, and disturb the matrix coherent to resist the extra force. So that, the mechanical properties of the composite is less than the pure 6061Al alloy[17].

As stated above, we conclude that at higher temperature ($\geq 250^{\circ}\text{C}$), the matrix metal become soften, then the particles may debond with the matrix, left the voids, and reduce the resistant strength. Because the matrix metal affect significantly the composite characteristics, and determine the mechanical behavior of the composite at higher temperature, in order to increase the compressive strength of composites at elevated temperature, a well control heat treatment process is recommended.

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Fig. 1: Transverse micrograph of 10/10/6061

Fig. 2: The compressive true stress-strain curve of 6061Al alloy and 10/10/6061Al composite at RT and 400°C

Fig. 3: The compressive true stress of 10/10/6061Al composite and pure 6061Al alloy at various temperature.

Fig. 4: The microstructure of the compressive fracture surface of SiCp 10/10/6061Al composite at 400°C

PROPERTIES OF DISCONTINUOUSLY REINFORCED COPPER MATRIX COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: Some properties of copper matrix composites based on three typical binary copper alloys (CuSn, CuCr and CuAl) and reinforced with a 13% V_f (volume fraction) of a mixture of both graphite flakes and δ -alumina short fibers have been studied. The hardness of the composites is practically similar to that measured for the unreinforced matrices, although it is higher for the composites manufactured with the highest volume V_f of δ -alumina short fibers (7%). Moreover, the composites have shown a lower coefficient of thermal expansion between the room and 400°C temperatures in comparison with their unreinforced matrices. On the other hand, the bronze based composite has excellent wear resistance and a lower coefficient of friction with respect to its matrix alloy. The tribological properties of this composite are mainly attributed to the thin layer of graphite at the surface of the wear track impeding metal-to-metal contact.

KEYWORDS: Copper matrix composites, graphite, alumina, foundry technique, hardness, coefficient of thermal expansion, coefficient of friction, wear behaviour.

INTRODUCTION

The need for quality in present industrial standards has made Metal Matrix Composites into a relevant and attractive alternative to unreinforced alloys in many components and applications. Copper Matrix Composites (CuMCs) are a new field, recently approached in the USA and Japan, which potentially offers several great advantages and possibilities of application in different industrial fields [1]. Initially, the leading factor for the development of these new materials was weight reduction and the improvement in reliability required by the aerospace industry. However, in recent years it has been clear that many other advantages can also be obtained by reinforcing copper alloys with discontinuous reinforcements such as particles or short fibers. Specifically, hardness, hot strength and above all wear resistance, can be drastically improved by the addition of a hard or a lubricant reinforcing phase (typical V_f : 5-25%) to the copper based alloy [2].

Due to the novelty of CuMCs, many studies are still required to characterize their properties and in use behaviour before their application at industrial scale. Specially interesting is the study of the wear mechanisms and behaviour, due to the large number of components made of bronzes, brasses or other copper alloys where wear is the main operating condition. Although the wear process has been extensively investigated in typical wear resistance materials, and is partially known in the case of aluminium based composites containing solid lubricants and/or hard ceramic particles [3-4], almost no study is available in the open literature on wear or lubricating properties of CuMCs.

Taking into account this situation, the main objective of this work was to determine some properties of discontinuously reinforced CuMCs, manufactured by a typical and widely applied foundry technique and then, compare them with those shown by the same unreinforced copper alloys. The materials selected for this study were composites based on three different binary copper alloys (Cu-Sn, Cu-Al and Cu-Cr), reinforced with a mixture of both graphite flakes and δ -alumina short fibers. The final reinforcement V_f was 13% for all the composites studied.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The materials selected for their characterization in the present study are three commercial copper alloys either unreinforced or reinforced with a mixture of both δ -alumina short fibers ($L=200 \mu\text{m}$ and $D=3.2 \mu\text{m}$) and graphite flakes ($160 \mu\text{m}$ average size). The composites were produced by a well-known foundry technique and reinforced with a mixture of both reinforcements whose V_f varied from 6% to 7% and lead to a total V_f of 13% for each composite, depending on the mechanical and tribomechanical properties required. The unreinforced copper alloys were processed by the same foundry technique, under similar working conditions, in order to compare later on the properties obtained with those shown by the corresponding composites.

The different materials manufactured and tested in the present study are summarized in the following Table 1.

Table 1: Materials manufactured and tested

Matrix (% given by weight)	Type of Reinforcement	V_f (%)	Material State
Cu-12%Sn	None	-	As-cast
Cu-12%Sn	δ -Alumina short fibers Graphite Flakes	6-7 7-6	As-cast
Cu-10%Al-5%Ni-5%Fe	None	-	As-cast
Cu-10%Al-5%Ni-5%Fe	δ -Alumina short fibers Graphite Flakes	6-7 7-6	As-cast
Cu-1%Cr-0.2%Zr	None	-	As-cast
Cu-1%Cr-0.2%Zr	δ -Alumina short fibers Graphite Flakes	6 7	As-cast

A representative microstructure of the different CuMCs produced for the present research work is shown in the following Fig.1. The graphite flakes and the δ -alumina short fibers are uniformly distributed inside the copper based matrix and no significant porosity is observed.

Fig.1: Microstructure of a CuSn/Graphite ($V_f=7\%$) - Alumina ($V_f=6\%$) composite

Both Brinell and Rockwell B were used to estimate the hardness of the composites and the corresponding unreinforced copper alloys, following the standards UNE 7422 and UNE 7424 respectively. The steel ball indenter used for these measurements had a diameter of either 10 mm or 1.5875 mm, for Brinell and Rockwell hardness respectively. In general, the measurement of macrohardness such as Rockwell or Brinell are more suitable than microhardness (e.g., Vickers) because of the typical great dispersion and variation of microhardness in the MMCs due to their usual complex microstructure.

Moreover, the Coefficient of Thermal Expansion (CTE) was measured following the standard ASTM (E228-85) through an Adamel L'Homargy DT 1000 dilatometer. The measurements were carried out with cylindrical test specimens of 2 mm in diameter and 12.5 mm in length, at a heating rate of 2 °C/min between the room and 400 °C temperatures.

Finally, the coefficient of friction and the wear behaviour studies have been performed for the CuSn bronze alloy, and its corresponding manufactured based composite, which is the most usual alloy for mechanical components such as bearings[5]. For that particular application, this alloy requires excellent tribological properties (low coefficient of friction and high wear resistance) under service conditions.

The dry sliding wear and friction tests were carried out in air under unlubricated conditions through a Biceri universal wear test machine. It was used either in the pin-on-reciprocating-plate mode for wear testing or in the pin-on-disk mode for friction tests. For the pin, a bearing ball (10 mm in diameter) made of steel AISI-54100 (UNE F-131) was used. The ball was gripped and the wear samples were cut and machined in squares of 40 mm side. In both cases, the samples were polished using a 3 μm diamond paste and cleaned with alcohol before and after each test. The roughness of the polished bronze, measured with a HOMMEL T 1000 profilometer gave a medium R_a value close to 0.02 μm , while the composite R_a values

suffered a rather great dispersion of between 0.1 μm and 0.6 μm . The samples were weighted accurately before and after each test for further plotting the sample weight loss vs. test conditions. For both the friction and the wear study, each test was repeated three times and the mean value was used for the analysis of the results. The coefficient of friction was calculated using the measurement of change in voltage given by a transducer connected to the wear machine.

The friction tests were carried out at a fixed velocity (V), load (P) and test duration (t) of V=235 mm/s, P=500 g and 200 g, t=30 min., while the wear behaviour was studied by varying the load applied on the sample and the sliding speed. The values tested for both parameters are shown in the Table 2.

Table 2: Wear test conditions

Load (g)	Speed (mm/s)
2.34	67
7.02	100
10.53	133

Optical microscopy was used in order to study the microstructure and detect physical changes in the tribo-deformed surfaces.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Hardness

The following Table 3 summarizes the main results obtained for both the copper matrices and the CuMCs tested.

Table 3: Measured hardness for the different materials tested

Matrix (% given by weight)	V _f Graphite (%)	V _f Alumina (%)	Hardness
Cu-10%Al-5%Ni-5%Fe	-	-	86-88 HRb
	7	6	82-85 HRb
	6	7	88-91 HRb
Cu-12%Sn	-	-	60-67 HRb
	-	-	102 HB5
	7	6	60-67 HRb
	6	7	100-102 HB5
Cu-1%Cr-0.2%Zr	-	-	60-63 HB5
	7	6	69-70 HB5